

Epi- π Normal Spaces in Topological Spaces

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Abstract. The aim of this paper is to introduce and study a new class of normal spaces, called epi π -normal spaces, which lies between epi-normal and epi-almost normal spaces, and epi-normal and epi-quasi normal spaces. Interrelation among some existing variants of normal spaces is discussed and characterizations of epi π -normal space with some existing variants of normal spaces are obtained. We also proved that epi π -normal space is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspace. We also investigate the relationships among epi π -normal spaces with other weak separation axioms. We show that this property is a topological, a semi-regularization and an additive property.

Key words and phrases: epi-normal, epi π -normal, epi-almost normal, epi-quasi normal, epi-softly normal, epi-mildly normal, epi-partly regular, epi-softly regular and epi-almost regular spaces.

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1. Introduction

In 1968, Zaitsev [37] introduced the notion of quasi normality is a weaker form of normality and obtained its properties. In 1970, the concept of almost normality was introduced by Singal and Arya [26]. In 1973, the notion of mild normality was introduced by Shchepin [23] and, Singal and Singal [28] independently. In 1990, Lal and Rahman [19] further investigated the notions of quasi normal and mildly normal spaces. In 2008, Kalantan [12] introduced π -normal topological spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2000, Dontchev and Noiri [8] introduced the notion of π g-closed sets and by using these sets, obtained a new characterization of quasi normal space. In 2015, Sharma and Kumar [30] introduced a new class of normal spaces called softly normal and obtained a characterization of softly normal space. In 2016, Alzahrani and Kalantan [14] studied epi-normality and obtained their properties. In 2018, Kumar and Sharma [17] introduced the concepts of softly regular and partly regular spaces and obtained characterizations of softly regular spaces. In 2018, Kalantan and Alshammari [15] introduced epi-mildly normal spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 2020, Alshammari [3] introduced the concept of epi-almost normality and obtained their properties. In 2021, Thabit et al. [36] introduced the concept of epi-quasi normality and obtained their properties.

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of normal spaces, called epi π -normal spaces, which lies between epi-normal and epi-almost normal spaces, and epi-normal and epi-quasi normal spaces. We also proved that epi π -normal space is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspace. We also investigate the relationships among epi π -normal spaces with other weak separation axioms.

2. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, τ) (or simply X , Y and Z) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A of a space X is said to be **regularly open** or **open domain** [18] if it is the interior of its own closure or, equivalently, if it is the interior of some closed set. A complement of an open domain subset of X is called **closed domain** (or a subset A is said to be **regular open** (resp. **regular closed**) if $A \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$ (resp. $A \subset \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$). The finite union of regular open sets is said to be π -**open** [37]. The complement of a π -open set is said to be π -**closed**. The set of real numbers is denoted by \mathfrak{R} . If \mathfrak{T} and \mathfrak{T}_1 are two topologies on a non-empty set X such that $\mathfrak{T}_1 \subset \mathfrak{T}$, then \mathfrak{T}_1 is called a topology **coarser** than \mathfrak{T} , and \mathfrak{T} is called **finer** [10]. Two sets A and B of X are said to be **separated** [9, 10, 22] if there exist two disjoint-open subsets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is **Hausdorff** (or a **T_2 -space** [10]), if for each two distinct points $x, y \in X$, there exist two open-subsets U and V of X such that $x \in U$, $y \in V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is **completely Hausdorff** (or a **Urysohn space** [10, 31]), if for each two distinct-points $a, b \in X$ there exist two open subsets U and V of X such that $a \in U$, $b \in V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$. A space X is **normal** [10] if any pair of disjoint-closed subsets A and B of X can be separated. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an **epi-regular** [4] (**epi-almost regular** [36]) space if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}' on X which is coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a T_3 -regular (resp. T_1 -almost regular) space. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is **sub-metrizable** space [11] if there exists a metric d on X such that the topology \mathfrak{T}_d on X generated by d is coarser than \mathfrak{T} . A topology on X generated by the family of all open-domain subsets, denoted by \mathfrak{T}_s , that is coarser than \mathfrak{T} , and the space (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is called the **semi-regularization** of X , and a space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called **semi-regular** if $\mathfrak{T} = \mathfrak{T}_s$ [21].

2.1 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is

1. **almost-regular** [25] space if for each $x \in X$ and for each closed-domain set F in X such that $x \notin F$, there exist two disjoint-open subsets U and V such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$.
2. **softly regular** [17] if for every π -closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist two open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.
3. **partly regular** [17] if for every point x and every π -open set U containing x , there is an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.
4. **weakly regular** [25] if for every point x and every regularly open set U containing x , there is an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.
5. **π -normal** [12] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed, there exist two disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.
6. **almost normal** [26], if for any two disjoint-closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is closed-domain, can be separated.
7. **quasi normal** [37] if for every pair of disjoint π -closed subsets A and B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.
8. **mildly normal** [28] if for any pair of disjoint closed-domain subsets A and B of X can be separated.
9. **softly normal** [30] if for any two disjoint closed subsets A and B of X , one of which is π -closed and other is regularly closed, there exist two disjoint open sets U and V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2.2 Remark. For a subset of a space, we have following implications [8]:

regular open $\Rightarrow \pi$ -open \Rightarrow open

Where none of the implications are reversible.

2.3 Remark. By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram [17]:

Where none of the implications is reversible.

2.3 Remark. By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram [30]:

normal \Rightarrow π -normal \Rightarrow almost normal \Rightarrow softly normal \Rightarrow mildly normal

and

normal \Rightarrow π -normal \Rightarrow quasi normal \Rightarrow softly normal \Rightarrow mildly normal

Where none of the implications is reversible.

3. Epi π -normal Spaces

3.1 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi-normal** [4] if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X that is coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_4 .

3.2 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi-almost normal** [3] if there exists a coarser topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_2 (or Hausdorff) almost normal.

3.3 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi-quasi normal** [35] if there exists a coarser topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_2 -quasi normal.

3.4 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi-mildly normal** [15] if there exists a coarser topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_2 -mildly normal.

3.5 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi-softly normal** space if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X , which is coarser than \mathfrak{T} , such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_2 -softly-normal.

3.6 Definition. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be an **epi- π normal** if there exists a coarser topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_2 - π -normal.

3.7 Remark. By the definitions stated above, we have the following diagram []:

A \Rightarrow B \Rightarrow C \Rightarrow D \Rightarrow E \Rightarrow F

and

A \Rightarrow B \Rightarrow C \Rightarrow G \Rightarrow E \Rightarrow F

Where none of the implications are reversible, as shown by the following examples:

A = submetrizability, B = epi-normal, C = epi π -normal, D = epi-almost normal, E = epi-softly normal, F = epi-mildly normal, G = epi-quasi normal

For example, the square of the Sorgenfrey line, see [31], is epi-normal as well as epi π -normal spaces which is not normal. It is epi-normal because it is submetrizable, since, by definitions, any submetrizable space is epi-normal. The converse of the last statement is not true in general. For example, $\omega_1 + 1$ is epi-normal being T_2 -compact, hence T_4 . But it is not submetrizable, because if $\omega_1 + 1$ was submetrizable, then there would be a metric d on $\omega_1 + 1$ such that the topology \mathfrak{T}_d on $\omega_1 + 1$ generated by d is coarser than the usual ordered topology. This means that $(\omega_1 + 1, \mathfrak{T}_d)$ is perfectly normal. So, the closed set $\{\omega_1\}$ is a G_δ -set in $(\omega_1 + 1, \mathfrak{T}_d)$, i.e., $\{\omega_1\} = \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} U_n$, where $U_n \in \mathfrak{T}_d$, hence U_n is open in the usual ordered topology on $\omega_1 + 1$, which is a contradiction. Epi-normality and normality do not imply each other. For example, the Niemytzki plane is epi-normal being submetrizable, but it is not normal by Jones' lemma. Any indiscrete space which has more than one element is an example of a normal space which is not epi-normal.

3.7 Example. The space $X = \mathfrak{R}^{\omega_1}$ [1, Example 0.3], is Tychonoff, separable, not normal and every regularly-closed (resp. π -closed) in \mathfrak{R}^{ω_1} depends on a countable set. Kalantan in [1] has shown that \mathfrak{R}^{ω_1} is a quasi normal space. Thus, \mathfrak{R}^{ω_1} is softly normal. Since \mathfrak{R}^{ω_1} is a Tychonoff softly normal space, it is epi-softly normal. So, \mathfrak{R}^{ω_1} is an example of an epi-softly normal Tychonoff space, which is not normal.

3.8 Example. The simplified Arens square topology [31, Example 81], is Hausdorff, semi regular, Lindelöf, σ -compact and with a σ -locally finite base, and it is neither completely Hausdorff, Urysohn, regular, normal nor locally compact. Since X is semi regular and not a regular space, we get X is not almost regular. Since X is T_1 and not almost regular, we obtain X is not an almost normal space. Since X is a quasi normal space [35], so X is softly normal as well as mildly normal. Thus, X is a Hausdorff softly normal space. Hence, it is an epi-softly normal space. Therefore, the simplified Arens square topology is an example of an epi-softly normal space that is neither epi-almost normal nor epi-regular. It is also a Hausdorff semi regular softly normal space. Thus, the simplified Arens square topology is an epi-softly normal, T_1 -softly normal space, which is neither epi-almost regular, almost regular nor almost normal.

3.9 Example. The telophase topology [31, Example 73], is a T_1 , compact, Lindelöf, paracompact space and with a σ -locally finite base, and it is neither Hausdorff, normal, regular, semi regular nor semi normal. It is easy to show that X is an almost-regular space. Since X is a paracompact almost-regular space, so it is π -normal as well as almost-normal, softly-normal and mildly-normal. Since X is not Hausdorff, it is neither epi- π normal, epi-mildly normal, epi-softly normal nor epi-regular. Since it is T_1 almost regular, we get X is an epi-almost regular space. Thus, the telophase topology is an example of an epi-almost regular softly normal compact (Lindelöf, paracompact) space with a σ -locally finite base, which is neither epi-softly normal nor epi-regular.

3.10 Example. The relatively prime integer topology and the prime integer topology [31, Example 60, 61], are Hausdorff, semi regular and Lindelöf spaces, which are not Urysohn. Since the only disjoint regularly-closed subsets in both spaces are X and \emptyset , both spaces are mildly normal. Thus, the relative prime integer and the prime integer topologies are epi-mildly normal being Hausdorff mildly normal spaces. Since the closures of any two proper-open subsets in both spaces have a non-empty intersection, they are not softly normal. Hence, they are neither quasi normal nor almost normal not π -normal spaces. Since they are semi regular and not regular spaces, they are neither almost regular nor almost completely regular. Since the two spaces are not Urysohn, they are neither epi-normal, epi π -normal, epi-almost normal nor epi-regular spaces.

3.11 Example. The ordinal space $\omega_1 + 1$ is an epi-normal space, hence epi π -normal but which is not submetrizable [4]. Any uncountable indiscrete space is an example of a softly-normal as well as mildly normal spaces that is not epi-softly normal being not Hausdorff. The Niemytzki plane topology [31], is an epi-softly normal space, which is not normal.

3.12 Example. The particular point topology $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{T}_p)$, the finite complement topology $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{CF})$ and the countable-complement topology $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{CC})$ are almost-regular and softly normal spaces because the only regularly-closed sets in which are \mathfrak{R} and \emptyset [31]. Thus, $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{T}_p)$, $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{CF})$ and $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{CC})$ are softly normal spaces, which are not epi-softly normal because they are not Hausdorff.

3.13 Example. The integer broom topology [31, Example 121], is a T_0 , normal, semi normal, compact, Lindelöf and paracompact space, which is neither T_1 , regular nor semi regular. Thus, X is an almost normal, softly normal and mildly normal space. Since X is not a T_1 -space, it is neither an epi-regular, epi-mildly normal, epi-softly normal nor epi-normal space. Therefore, the integer broom topology is an example of a softly normal compact (Lindelöf, paracompact) space, which is neither epi-softly normal nor epi-regular.

3.14 Example. The irregular lattice topology [31, Example 79] is a Urysohn Lindelöf space that is neither regular, normal, nor semi-regular [31]. It is also a mildly normal space that is not a softly normal space [1]. Hence, it is neither a quasi normal, an almost normal, nor a semi normal space. Since every almost regular Lindelöf space is a quasi normal space as well as mildly normal space [19], and X is Lindelöf not quasi normal, it is not an almost regular space. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Hausdorff mildly normal space, it is epi-mildly normal.

3.15 Example. Let A be the linearly ordered set $\{1, 2, 3, \dots, \omega, \dots, -3, -2, -1\}$ with the interval topology, and if Z^+ is the set of positive integer with the discrete topology, we define $X = A \times Z^+$ together with two ideal points a and $-a$. The topology \mathfrak{T} on X is determined by the product topology on $A \times Z^+$ together with basis neighborhoods $M_n^+(a) = \{a\} \cup \{(i, j) : i < \omega, j > n\}$ and $M_n^-(a) = \{-a\} \cup \{(i, j) : i > \omega, j > n\}$ [31]. This topology is called **minimal Hausdorff topology**. The minimal Hausdorff topology is a Hausdorff, semiregular, σ -compact, Lindelöf, second countable, almost compact space and with a σ -locally finite base, that is neither completely Hausdorff, Urysohn, regular, normal, paracompact, nor compact [31]. Since X is a semi-regular not regular space, thus X is not an almost regular space. Since X is a T_1 not almost regular space, it is not an almost normal space. Note that each basic open neighborhood is an open domain subset of X . Since X is not Urysohn (not completely Hausdorff), it is neither epi-almost normal nor epi-regular. It can be observed that every semi-regular epi-almost regular space is an epi-regular space [34]. Since X is a semi-regular not epi-regular space, we conclude that X cannot be an epi-almost regular space.

3.16 Example. The countable complement extension topology [31, Example 63], is Hausdorff, Urysohn, Lindelöf, not semi-regular, and any compact subset is finite [31]. Since X is an almost regular, Hausdorff quasi normal space, it is an epi-quasi normal space that is neither normal nor almost normal. In fact, the countable complement extension topology is an epi-normal space because, $\wp \subset \mathfrak{T}$ where \wp is the Euclidean topology on \mathbb{R} , which is coarser than \mathfrak{T} .

3.17 Example. The modified fort space: [31, Example 27], let $X = \mathbb{N} \cup \{x_1, x_2\}$. Define a topology \mathfrak{T} on X as follows: any set $U \subset \mathbb{N}$ is open. Any subset U containing either x_1 or x_2 is open if and only if $X - U$ is finite [31]. Then, X is a compact T_1 space that is neither Hausdorff, regular, semi-regular, normal nor first countable. Since the closure of any open set containing x_1 (or x_2) contains x_1, x_2 [31], it is easy to show that any closed domain in the modified fort space is either finite clopen or infinite containing both x_1 and x_2 . Thus, X is an almost regular space. Since X is compact almost regular, we have X is π normal. Hence, it is a quasi normal space that is not semi normal. Thus, X is a T_1 -almost regular space that is neither epi-regular nor epi π -normal not epi quasi normal because it is not Hausdorff. Therefore, the modified fort space is an example of a T_1 -almost regular space that is neither epi-regular nor epi-quasi normal. It is also an example of a quasi normal space that is not epi-quasi normal.

4. Properties of epi π -normal spaces with separation axioms

4.1 Theorem. Every epi π -normal space is T_2 .

Proof. Easy to prove.

4.2 Proposition [21]. (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Hausdorff if and only if (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is Hausdorff.

The situation is quite different for the T_0 and T_1 properties.

4.3 Proposition [21]. If (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is T_0 (resp. T_1) then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is T_0 (resp. T_1), but the converse is false.

4.4 Proposition [21]. (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Urysohn (resp. functionally Hausdorff) if and only if (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is Urysohn (resp. functionally Hausdorff).

On the other hand, the Urysohn (or $T_2^{\frac{1}{2}}$) property behaves like T_2 . Steen and Seebach [31, page 13-15] call a Urysohn space by the term completely Hausdorff, and use Urysohn for spaces called functionally Hausdorff by other authors.

4.5 Theorem. Every epi π -normal space is completely Hausdorff.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be any epi π -normal space and \mathfrak{T}' is the witness of epi π -normality. Since every π -normal T_1 -space is almost regular, so \mathfrak{T}' is almost regular. Let \mathfrak{T}_s be the semi-regularization of \mathfrak{T}' . Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is Hausdorff almost regular space, \mathfrak{T}_s is Hausdorff regular space [21], and hence it is a completely Hausdorff. By using Proposition 3 [21], (X, \mathfrak{T}') is completely Hausdorff. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is completely Hausdorff.

Since every π -normal T_1 -space is almost regular and every almost regular semi-regular is regular [21], then we have the following theorem.

4.6 Theorem. In semi-regular space, epi π -normality and epi-normality are equivalent.

4.7 Theorem. Epi π -normal space is topological property.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be any epi π -normal space. Assume that $(X, \mathfrak{T}) \cong (Y, \mathfrak{S})$. Let \mathfrak{T}' be a coarser topology on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is Hausdorff π -normal space. Let $f : (X, \mathfrak{T}) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{S})$ be a homeomorphism and define \mathfrak{S}' on Y by $\mathfrak{S}' = \{f(U) : U \in \mathfrak{T}'\}$. Then \mathfrak{S}' is a topology on Y coarser than \mathfrak{S} and (Y, \mathfrak{S}') is Hausdorff π -normal space. Therefore, (Y, \mathfrak{S}') is epi π -normal space. Hence (Y, \mathfrak{S}) is epi π -normal space.

4.8 Theorem. Epi π -normality is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspaces.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an epi π -normal space and (M, \mathfrak{T}_M) be a closed domain subspace of X . Then, there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}' on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Define \mathfrak{T}'_M on M by: $\mathfrak{T}'_M = \{M \cap U : U \in \mathfrak{T}'\}$. Then, $\mathfrak{T}'_M \subset \mathfrak{T}_M$, and hence, \mathfrak{T}'_M is a topology on M coarser than \mathfrak{T}_M . Since (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal space and (M, \mathfrak{T}'_M) is a closed domain subspace of X , thus (M, \mathfrak{T}'_M) is a Hausdorff π -normal subspace of (X, \mathfrak{T}') . Therefore, (M, \mathfrak{T}_M) is an epi π -normal space.

Since every closed-and-open (clopen) subset is a closed domain, thus:

4.9 Corollary. Epi π -normality is a hereditary property with respect to clopen subspaces.

4.10 Theorem. The sum $\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha$, where X_α is a space for each $\alpha \in \Delta$, is epi π -normal if and only if all spaces X_α are epi π -normal.

Proof. If the sum $(\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha, \bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} \mathfrak{T}_\alpha)$ is epi π -normal, then there exist \mathfrak{T}' topology on $\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha$, coarser than $\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} \mathfrak{T}_\alpha$ such that $(\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha, \mathfrak{T}')$ is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Since X_α is clopen in $\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha$, for each $\alpha \in \Delta$, $(X_\alpha, \mathfrak{T}'_\alpha)$, where $\mathfrak{T}'_\alpha = \{U \cap X_\alpha : U \in \mathfrak{T}'\}$, is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Thus all spaces X_α are epi π -normal as $(X_\alpha, \mathfrak{T}'_\alpha)$ is coarser topology than $(X_\alpha, \mathfrak{T}_\alpha)$.

Conversely, if all the X_α 's are epi π -normal, then there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}'_α on X_α for each $\alpha \in \Delta$, coarser than \mathfrak{T}_α such that $(X_\alpha, \mathfrak{T}'_\alpha)$ is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Since T_2 and π -normality are both additive [10], then $(\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha, \bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} \mathfrak{T}'_\alpha)$ is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Therefore $(\bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} X_\alpha, \bigoplus_{\alpha \in \Delta} \mathfrak{T}_\alpha)$ is epi π -normal space.

4.11 Theorem [32]. If X is a π -normal countably compact space and M is a Hausdorff paracompact first countable space, then the product $X \times M$ is a π -normal space.

4.12 Theorem. If X is epi π -normal countably compact and M is Hausdorff paracompact first countable, then $X \times M$ is epi π -normal.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be any epi π -normal countably compact space. Then there exists coarser topology \mathfrak{T}' on X such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is Hausdorff π -normal space. Since the coarser topology of countably compact is countably compact, so $(X, \mathfrak{T}') \times M$ is Hausdorff π -normal, by **Theorem 9** of [13]. Thus $X \times M$ is epi π -normal.

Since every compact space is paracompact and every metrizable space is paracompact first countable, we get the following corollaries:

4.13 Corollary. If X is an epi π -normal countably compact (resp. compact) space and M is a metrizable space, then the product $X \times M$ is an epi π -normal space.

4.14 Theorem. (X, \mathfrak{T}) is soft normality if and only if the semi-regularization of X is π -normal.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be softly normal space, A and B be disjoint closed sets in \mathfrak{T}_s such that A is regular closed in \mathfrak{T}_s . Hence, $B = E \cap F$, where E and F are regular closed sets in \mathfrak{T}_s . Thus, A and B are disjoint closed sets in \mathfrak{T} such that A is regular closed (since every regular closed set is closed) and B is π -closed. By soft normality, there exist two open sets U and V such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \emptyset$. Then there exist two disjoint regular open sets U_s and V_s containing U and V respectively, see [7]. Thus, A and B are separated by two open sets in \mathfrak{T}_s . Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is π -normality.

Conversely, let A and B be disjoint closed sets in \mathfrak{T} such that A is π -closed and B is regular closed. Hence A and B are disjoint closed sets in \mathfrak{T}_s such that B is regular closed. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is π -normal, there exist disjoint open sets U and V containing A and B , respectively. Therefore (X, \mathfrak{T}) is softly normal.

It is clear from the definition that any T_2 (or Hausdorff) π -normal space is epi π -normal, just take the coarser topology equal the same topology. But here we have something stronger.

4.15 Corollary. Every Hausdorff softly normal space is epi π -normal.

Proof. Since every π -normal is softly normal space.

4.16 Corollary. A semi-regular space is softly normal if and only if it is π -normal.

4.17 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is semi-normal π -normal space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is normal space.

Proof. Let B be any open set containing a closed set A in (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) . By semi-normality, there exists an open set U such that $A \subset U \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(U)) \subset B$. Since $\text{int}(\text{cl}(U))$ is regular open and using Theorem 4.14, there exists an open set V in (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) such that $A \subset V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset \text{int}(\text{cl}(U)) \subset B$. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is normal space.

4.18 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is semi-normal softly normal space and \mathfrak{T}_s is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi-normal.

4.19 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is semi-normal π -normal space and \mathfrak{T}_s is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi-normal.

In [26] proved that any almost normal; almost regular space is almost completely Hausdorff and any π -normal almost regular space is almost completely Hausdorff, since every π -normal space is almost normal space [12] we use this fact to prove the following Corollaries.

4.20 Corollary. If X is π -normal almost regular then X is completely Hausdorff space.

4.21 Corollary. If X is π -normal almost regular then X is epi π -normal.

4.22 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is π -normal space and \mathfrak{T}_s is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is completely Hausdorff space.

Proof. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is softly normal space, then the semi-regularization of X is π -normal, hence almost regular. Moreover, almost regular π -normal is completely Hausdorff space, by Corollary 2.19, so the semi-regularization of X is completely Hausdorff space. Therefore (X, \mathfrak{T}) is completely Hausdorff.

4.23 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is π -normal almost compact and \mathfrak{T}_s is T_1 , then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi-mildly normal.

Proof. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is π -normal, then the semi-regularization of X is almost regular. Moreover, the coarser topology of almost compact is almost compact. So, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is almost compact. But every almost regular almost compact is mildly normal [28]. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is mildly normal. By Theorem 2.19, we conclude that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi-mildly normal.

4.24 Theorem. Every epi π -normal semi-regular is epi-regular.

As every weakly regular, paracompact space is a π -normal [32, 34], then we have the following corollary.

4.25 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi-regular and the witness of epi-regularity (X, \mathfrak{T}') is paracompact, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi π -normal.

5. Relationships of epi π -normal spaces with compactness

Now, we study the relationships among epi π -normality, paracompactness, weakly regularity, almost regularity, partly regularity and soft regularity. First, we need to recall the following definitions:

5.1 Definition. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be a topological space. Then, the space X is called:

1. almost compact [20] if each open cover of X has a finite subfamily such that the closures of whose members cover X .

2. nearly compact (resp. **countably nearly compact**) [26, 27] if every open domain (resp. countable open domain) cover η of X has a finite subcover.

3. nearly paracompact (resp. **countably nearly paracompact**) [25] if every open domain (resp. countable open domain) cover of X has a locally finite open refinement.

It can be observed that every compact (countably compact, nearly compact) space is paracompact (resp. countably paracompact, nearly paracompact). Recall that: a space X is called a weakly regular space if every point $x \in X$ and every open domain subset U of X contains x , there exists an open set V in X such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$ [25]. Some characterizations of weakly regular spaces by using π -open and π -closed sets have been given in [32, 34].

compact \Rightarrow nearly compact \Rightarrow almost compact

5.2 Theorem [32, 34]. Every weakly regular, paracompact space is a π -normal space.

Since every almost regular space is a weakly regular space, every nearly paracompact Hausdorff space is an almost regular space and every compact space is paracompact, we obtain the following corollaries:

5.3 Corollary [32, 34]. Every almost-regular, paracompact space is a π -normal space.

Since every partly regular space is a weakly regular space and every softly regular space is a weakly regular space.

5.4 Corollary [17]. Every partly-regular, paracompact space is a π -normal space.

5.5 Corollary [17]. Every softly-regular, paracompact space is a π -normal space.

5.6 Corollary [32, 34]. Every weakly-regular, compact space is a π -normal space.

5.7 Corollary [32, 34]. Every almost-regular, compact space is a π -normal space.

5.8 Corollary [17]. Every partly-regular, compact space is a π -normal space.

5.9 Corollary [17]. Every softly-regular, compact space is a π -normal space.

Since every paracompact Hausdorff space is almost regular space.

5.10 Corollary [32, 34]. Every paracompact Hausdorff space is a π -normal space.

Since every almost-normal, T_1 -space is almost regular space and every π -normal, T_1 -space is almost regular space [32, 34]. Since every almost compact Urysohn space is almost regular space.

A quasi normal, nearly paracompact space is not necessary to be an almost regular space as shown by the following counterexample.

5.11 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and let $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$ be a topology on X . Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a π -normal nearly paracompact space. Note that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not an almost regular space because $\{b, c\}$ is closed domain, $a \in \{b, c\}$ and there do not exist two disjoint open sets containing a and $\{b, c\}$, respectively.

Next, we present the following new definitions:

5.12 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called an **epi-almost regular** [36] space if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_1 -almost regular space.

5.13 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called an **epi-softly regular** space if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_1 -softly regular space.

5.14 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is called an **epi-partly regular** space if there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}_1 on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}_1) is a T_1 -partly regular space.

Clearly, every epi-almost regular space is a T_1 space, every epi-regular space is an epi-almost regular space, and every epi-regular space is Urysohn. Since, every epi-partly regular space is an epi-almost regular and every epi-softly regular space is an epi-almost regular. Lal and Rahman in [19], proved that “If X is an almost regular in which every π -closed set is an almost compact, then X is quasi-normal”. Thabit and Kamarulhaili [34] improved the following Theorem and Corollaries:

5.15 Theorem [34]. If X is an almost regular in which every closed set is an almost compact, then X is a π -normal.

5.16 Theorem. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-almost regular almost compact space (in which every closed set is an almost compact), and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 -space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an epi-almost regular almost space (in which every closed set is an almost compact) and (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) be its semi-regularization. Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is an almost regular T_1 almost compact compact space. Hence, it is a T_3 -almost compact space [31]. Since every almost regular almost compact (in which every closed set is an almost compact) space is a π -normal space, Corollary 5.2, we get (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Hence, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

Since every nearly compact space is an almost compact space, we get the following corollaries:

5.17 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-almost regular nearly compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.18 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-partly regular almost compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.19 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-partly regular nearly compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.20 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-softly regular almost compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.21 Corollary. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-softlyly regular nearly compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.22 Theorem. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-almost regular Hausdorff space and the witness of epi-almost regularity (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a paracompact space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is epi π -normal.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an epi-almost regular Hausdorff space and (X, \mathfrak{T}') be the witness of epi-almost regularity. Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff almost-regular paracompact space. Since every almost-regular paracompact space is π -normal [32, 34], we get (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space.

5.23 Theorem. Every epi π -normal almost-regular space is a Urysohn space.

Proof. It is obvious because every Hausdorff almost-regular space is Urysohn.

5.24 Corollary. Every almost regular non Urysohn space cannot be an epi π -normal space.

Since every epi π -normal space is Hausdorff and every almost normal T_1 -space is almost regular, we get:

5.25 Corollary. Every epi π -normal almost-normal space is an almost-regular space.

Since every epi-partially normal space is Hausdorff, any topology coarser than a nearly paracompact space is paracompact [21], and every Hausdorff paracompact space is normal, we conclude:

5.26 Corollary. Every nearly paracompact epi π -normal space is an epi-normal space.

6. Properties of epi π -normality with existing normal spaces

Since every C_2 -paracompact Fréchet space is an epi-normal space, and any Mrówka space $\psi(A)$ is an epi-normal space [15], we obtain the following corollaries:

6.1 Corollary 1. Every C_2 -paracompact Fréchet space (resp. Mrówka space $\psi(A)$) is an epi π -normal space.

Note that every extremally disconnected space is a π -normal space [12]. Thus, we obtain:

6.2 Corollary. Every extremally disconnected Hausdorff space is an epi π -normal space.

It can be observed that, any epi-quasi normal space may not be an extremally disconnected space, for example, the rational sequence topology $(\mathfrak{R}, \mathfrak{R}\mathfrak{S})$, [31, Example 65] is a Tychonoff epi-quasi normal space that is not extremally disconnected [31]. Any minimal Hausdorff space need not be a compact epi-quasi normal space, for example, the space in [15, Example 6] is a minimal Hausdorff space that is neither compact nor epi-quasi normal because it is not a quasi normal space.

It can be observed that, if (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an almost regular space, then its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a regular space [21], and every almost compact almost regular space is a mildly normal space [28].

6.3 Theorem. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an almost regular nearly compact space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 -space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-normal space, and hence, it is an epi π -normal space.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an almost regular space and (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) be its semi-regularization. Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a regular space [15]. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 -space, gives us (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_3 -space. In fact, a topology coarser than a nearly

compact space is a compact space. Thus, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a regular compact space. Since every regular compact space is a normal space, we obtain (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a Hausdorff normal space. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-normal space, and hence, it is an epi π -normal space.

6.4 Theorem. (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a π -normal space if and only if its semi regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a π -normal space.

Proof. Let A and B be any two disjoint-closed sets in the semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that A is π -closed and B is closed. Then, A is π -closed and B is closed in (X, \mathfrak{T}) . By π -normality of (X, \mathfrak{T}) , there exist two open-sets U and V in (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $A \subset U$, $B \subset V$ and $U \cap V = \phi$. Thus, there exist two disjoint-open sets U_s and V_s in (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) such that $U \subset U_s$ and $V \subset V_s$ [21]. So, we have $A \subset U_s$, $B \subset V_s$ and $U_s \cap V_s = \phi$. Hence, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a π -normal space.

Conversely, let (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) be a π -normal space. Let A and B be any two disjoint-closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that A is π -closed and B is closed. Then, A and B are disjoint closed-sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) such that A is π -closed and B is closed. By π -normality of (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) , there exist two disjoint open-sets U_s and V_s in (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) such that $A \subset U_s$ and $B \subset V_s$. Since $\mathfrak{T}_s \subset \mathfrak{T}$ and $U_s, V_s \in \mathfrak{T}_s$, we get U_s and V_s are disjoint open-sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Hence, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a π -normal space.

6.5 Corollary. π -normality is a semi-regularization property.

Note that, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Hausdorff space if and only if its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is Hausdorff [21]. Thus, we conclude:

6.6 Corollary. (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi π -normal space if and only if its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is an epi π -normal space.

6.7 Theorem. If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an almost-regular (resp. almost-completely regular) π -normal space and its semi regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 -space, then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Urysohn epi π -normal space..

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an almost-regular (resp. almost-completely regular) π -normal space and its semi regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) be a T_1 -space. Since the semi-regularization of an almost-regular (resp. almost-completely regular) space is regular (resp. completely-regular) [21], we obtain (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 -regular (resp. completely-regular) space, and hence it is a T_3 (resp. Tychonoff) space. Thus, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a Urysohn space, and hence it is Hausdorff. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Urysohn π -normal space. Hence, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Urysohn epi π -normal space.

6.8 Theorem [36]. A semi regularization of a semi-normal space is semi-normal

6.9 Theorem. Every epi π -normal semi normal space is an epi-normal space.

Proof. Let X be an epi π -normal semi normal space, and (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) be the semi-regularization of (X, \mathfrak{T}) . Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a Hausdorff π -normal semi normal space. Since every π -normal semi normal space is a normal space, thus (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a Hausdorff normal space. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-normal space.

Next we conclude the following corollaries:

6.10 Corollary. In a semi normal space X , the following statements are equivalent:

- (1) X is epi-normal.
- (2) X is epi π -normal.
- (3) X is epi-almost normal.
- (4) X is epi-softly normal.
- (5) X is epi-mildly normal.

6.11 Corollary. In a semi normal space X , the following statements are equivalent:

- (1) X is epi-normal.
- (2) X is epi π -normal.

- (2) X is epi-quasi normal.
- (3) X is epi-softly normal.
- (4) X is epi-mildly normal.

Since every paracompact (resp. compact) space is a θ -normal space, and every Hausdorff θ -normal space is normal [21], we conclude:

4.12 Corollary. Every epi π -normal paracompact (resp. compact) space is T_4 .

4.13 Corollary. Every epi-regular paracompact (resp. compact) space is an epi-normal space, and hence it is epi π -normal.

6.14 Theorem. Every Hausdorff nearly compact space is epi-normal (hence epi π -normal space).

Proof. Let \mathfrak{T}_s be semiregularization of \mathfrak{T} . Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a Hausdorff nearly compact space, \mathfrak{T}_s is a compact Hausdorff space [21]. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_4 -space. Therefore X is epi-normal space.

6.15 Theorem. Every epi π -normal space is an epi-regular space.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an epi π -normal space. Then, there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}' on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal space. Since every π -normal T_1 -space is an almost regular space, thus (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal almost regular space. Let \mathfrak{T}'_s be the semi-regularization of \mathfrak{T}' . Then, (X, \mathfrak{T}'_s) is a Hausdorff regular space. Since $\mathfrak{T}'_s \subset \mathfrak{T}' \subset \mathfrak{T}$, thus \mathfrak{T}'_s is a topology on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} and (X, \mathfrak{T}'_s) is a Hausdorff regular space. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-regular space.

6.16 Theorem. Every epi π -normal compact (resp. nearly compact, paracompact, nearly paracompact) space is an epi-normal space, and hence, it is an epi π -normal space.

Proof. We prove the case when X is paracompact and similarly for the other cases. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}) be an epi π -normal paracompact space. Then, there exists a topology \mathfrak{T}' on X coarser than \mathfrak{T} such that (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal paracompact space. By Theorem 6.15, we get (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff π -normal regular space (hence T_3 - π -normal). Since any regular paracompact space is normal, we obtain (X, \mathfrak{T}') is a Hausdorff normal space. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}) is an epi-normal space, and hence, it is an epi π -normal space.

6.17 Remark. It can be observed that:

- (1) Epi-quasi normality and σ -compactness are independent from each other. For example, the rational sequence topology is an epi-quasi normal space that is not σ -compact. The integer broom topology, Example 2.12, is a σ -compact space that is not epi-quasi normal. The uncountable discrete space is an epi-quasi normal space that is not σ -compact [31].
- (2) Quasi normality and first countability do not imply to Hausdorffness. For example, the odd-even topology [31, Example 6] is a first countable quasi normal space that is not Hausdorff. Hence, it is not epi-quasi normal.
- (3) Any almost regular quasi normal space need not be an epi-quasi normal space. For example, the uncountable indiscrete space is an almost regular quasi normal space that is not epi-quasi normal being not Hausdorff.
- (4) Any compact quasi normal space need not be epi-quasi normal. For example, the excluded point topology [31, Examples 13–15] is a compact quasi normal space that is not epi-quasi normal because it is not Hausdorff.
- (5) Semi-regularity (resp. semi normality) does not imply to epi-quasi normality. For example, the odd-even topology [31, Example 6] is both semi-regular and semi normal because it is both regular and normal as well as π -normal. But it is neither epi π -normal nor epi-quasi normal being not Hausdorff. The double pointed reals topology [31, Example 62] is a semi-regular space being regular, that is not epi-quasi normal being not Hausdorff.
- (6) If (X, \mathfrak{T}) is a quasi normal space, and its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, then it is not necessary to be completely Hausdorff (or Urysohn). For example, the minimal Hausdorff topology [31, Example 100] is quasi normal. Its semi-regularization (X, \mathfrak{T}_s) is a T_1 space, and (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not a completely Hausdorff space (hence not a Urysohn space).

(7) Since every almost regular Hausdorff space is a Urysohn space, and every epi-quasi normal space is Hausdorff, there is no an epi-quasi normal almost regular not Urysohn space X . In fact, every epi-quasi normal almost regular space is a Urysohn space, Theorem 5.22.

7. Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of normal spaces, called epi π -normal spaces, which lies between epi-normal and epi-almost normal, and epi-normal and epi-quasi normal. Interrelation among some existing variants of normal spaces is discussed and characterizations of these variants are obtained. We also proved that epi π -normal space is a topological property and it is a hereditary property with respect to closed domain subspace. We also investigate this property and present some examples that illustrate the relationships between epi π -normal spaces and other weaker versions of both epi-normal and epi-regular spaces. We show that this property is a topological, a semi-regularization and an additive property.

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